

TRANSFORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES AND TRENDS IN CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the growing need for the transformation of professional competencies in the new stage of development, marked by socio-economic changes, digital transformation, and innovative progress. The article also discusses changes in the education system aimed at training competitive professionals, focusing on competency-based curricula, mechanisms of lifelong learning, and retraining. The significance of collaboration between public social demand, employers, and educational institutions in shaping and transforming competencies is emphasized.*

Keywords: *competence, professional competency, future skills, competency model, transformation of competencies, creativity, innovation.*

Introduction

It is important to note that the "Uzbekistan 2030" Strategy identifies reforming the education system as a priority area, setting specific targets for training competitive personnel and aligning their knowledge and qualifications with international standards [1]. At the same time, modern globalization processes and the development of science and technology are shaping new trends at the international level in developing the professional competencies of future specialists. In particular, transformational models and new paradigms such as Industry 5.0, the Japanese concept of "Society 5.0," Education 4.0, University 4.0, and the HECI (Humanity, Ethics, Creativity, Imagination) concept reflect new guidelines in the development of modern education.

The analysis of international experience shows that a country's position in the Global Innovation Index is directly related to the level of development of science, invention, and technology transfer, the improvement of education quality, and the development of human capital and workforce potential. From this perspective, one of the strategic objectives of an innovation-driven economy today is the creation of modern education and human resource management (HRM) ecosystems aimed at the internationalization, globalization, and transformation of higher education, improving its quality, and developing the competencies of specialists, including the development of metacompetencies (soft skills) that ensure flexible adaptation to dynamic labor market trends.

This development naturally raises questions: to what extent does the quality of education and research at universities correspond to these global trends, and will specialists trained today be able to meet the demands of industry and the labor market in 2030–2050?

Literature analysis

The current pace of scientific and technological progress and the intensification of innovation transfer in education, science, and industry increase the need for research based on the latest methodological approaches to studying the content and structure of professional competence.

It should be emphasized that highlights the need to improve educational content, enhance the quality of instruction, diversify educational services aimed at developing professional competence, and implement a competency-based approach in higher education.

In scientific and pedagogical literature and explanatory dictionaries, the concept of "competence" is interpreted in various ways:

- as a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, and abilities necessary for the successful performance of a specific activity;
- as the ability to perform job functions in accordance with established requirements;
- as a criterion for the effectiveness of a specialist's professional activity.

Essentially, competence expresses the ability to effectively apply theoretical knowledge in practice and demonstrate a high level of professional skill, ability, and potential.

In UNESCO's international projects and documents, the core competency framework for specialists includes:

- professional competencies (literacy and competence in their professional field);
- ICT competencies (use of information and communication technologies, media literacy, technological culture, etc.);
- communication competencies;
- social competencies (ability to work in a group, tolerance, intercultural communication, gender sensitivity, etc.);
- personal competencies (motivation, empathy, self-esteem, creativity, critical thinking, ability to manage change, etc.) [8].

At the World Economic Forum in Davos (2020), during the discussion of "Skills for the Future," a key idea emerged: we are preparing specialists for a future we cannot yet clearly imagine. The primary goal of education, therefore, is to develop in specialists the skills that enable them to act effectively in conditions of uncertainty and change [8].

At the same forum, the 15 most in-demand competencies by 2030 were identified: analytical and critical thinking, resilience, creativity, leadership, stress tolerance, systems analysis, persuasion, a comprehensive approach to problem solving, customer focus, emotional intelligence, communication, self-management, civic responsibility, and others.

The research project "Foresight of Competencies 2030," implemented by the Skolkovo Moscow School of Management, found that technological change requires a revision of management models, an increased social demand for specialists with modern knowledge, and changes in professional training formats based on innovative approaches.

The report "Atlas of new professions 3.0" (Skolkovo, 2021) identifies 11 key competencies of the future: ecological thinking, time management, artistic creativity, project management, teamwork, interdisciplinary communication, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, etc. [4].

American researcher Richard Boyatzis emphasizes that the most important component of professional competence is emotional intelligence, which ensures a stable psycho-emotional state of an individual and contributes to the achievement of high results through the conscious management of emotions and their integration into cognitive processes [5].

Finnish researchers Aila Paaso and Kati Korento define the development of professional competence through a combination of practical experience, professional knowledge and skills, as well as a system of continuous self-development of the specialist.

Indonesian scholar Adnan Hakim defines professional competence as a person's ability to perform a specific activity based on knowledge, worldview, qualifications, and skills that meet the requirements of the profession [6].

Based on an analysis of scientific sources and international experience, the author concludes that the transformation of competencies is a continuous process and proposes corresponding development models.

Research Methodology

It should be noted that effective development of the professional competence of future specialists requires defining a system of competencies based on the requirements of qualification standards.

Qualification requirements represent a system of knowledge, abilities, and skills necessary for the successful performance of professional functions, as well as the level of training and skill of the specialist.

At the same time, the content of the professional competencies of future specialists should be considered in the following aspects:

- Methodological aspect - key competencies reflecting the goals, patterns, principles, and methods of the educational process;
- Technological aspect – specific competencies related to the design, planning, and implementation of the educational process, the selection of didactic tools and teaching methods;
- Innovative aspect – metacompetencies that ensure the effective organization of pedagogical and managerial activities, the creation and implementation of new forms and methods of teaching.

The development of a competency system based on qualification standards, employer requirements, and the needs of educational institutions is of great importance.

The online survey conducted as part of the study revealed that employers place particular importance on competencies such as analytical and creative thinking, optimal decision-making, time management, information interpretation, project management, cross-industry communication, entrepreneurial thinking, adaptability, and others.

Furthermore, the majority of specialists (57.4%), regardless of length of service, noted the need to continually update their knowledge and skills in accordance with innovative requirements.

Analysis and Results

The conducted scientific and pedagogical analysis and empirical research revealed that the transformation of professional competence is being implemented in the following areas:

- a) the development of a system of basic competencies based on state social mandates, employer requirements, and qualification standards;
- b) determining the level of competence development and identifying individual professional development needs using a diagnostic assessment system;
- c) improving the composition and content of competencies through the integration of innovative approaches and best international practices; and improving the quality of educational programs and resources focused on competence development.

Based on the analysis, the following pedagogical conditions for the transformation of professional competencies in the new stage of societal development were identified:

1. Organizational conditions – creating opportunities for independent professional and personal development and assessing its results.

2. Substantive conditions – improving educational content based on state standards, qualification requirements, curricula, digital technologies, and methodological frameworks.

3. Technological conditions – introducing innovative teaching methods (project-based, problem-based, case-based learning, gaming technologies, training, tutoring, facilitation, etc.), improving the professional skills of teachers.

4. Reflective conditions – providing a system for monitoring and qualimetry of the quality of professional competence, creating conditions for self-assessment and satisfaction with the results of professional activity.

Conclusions and suggestions

In the context of the rapid development of science and technology, the development of modern professional competencies that ensure the effective work of a specialist, mastery of digital technologies, research skills, and creativity are of particular importance. It is necessary to develop and implement adaptive, creatively oriented educational programs that meet the individual needs of specialists.

It can be stated that it is advisable to intensify the activities of Foresight centers that forecast future competencies and, based on their results, develop an innovative methodology for developing the professional competencies of future specialists.

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